

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-175-IE-10% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	100	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 2 175
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	290.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 290.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/8/2022 9:52:21 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 10:03:17 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.762	3387338	12.35	484618
2	6.197	3400644	12.40	453101
3	6.711	10221962	37.28	1228673
4	7.145	10410066	37.97	1241265

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-176-IE-10% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	100	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 2 176
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	290.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 290.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/8/2022 10:06:31 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 10:05:57 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.793	152531	0.54	21774
2	6.240	112850	0.40	11756
3	6.724	28073807	99.05	2934305
4	7.162	4079	0.01	-467